

SCOPE OF AYURVEDIC MEDICINE IN VETERINARY SCIENCE: BRIDGING ANCIENT KNOWLEDGE WITH MODERN ANIMAL HEALTHCARE

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, the traditional system of Indian medicine, offers a holistic approach that extends beyond human healthcare to include the treatment of animals and plants. This study explores the ancient roots and modern relevance of Ayurvedic veterinary science— *Pasu-Ayurveda* through the magnifying classical texts, current applications, and emerging scientific evidence. Fundamental treatises such as the *Shalihotra Samhita*, *Garuda Purana*, and *Atri Samhita* provide rich documentation of animal medicine, particularly for horses, cattle, and elephants. In contemporary contexts, some people are re-examining traditional Ayurvedic practices to see if they can help with modern health issues like antimicrobial resistance, residue-free animal products, and sustainable farming. Evidence-based applications include Ayurvedic interventions for mastitis in dairy cattle, phytogenic feed additives in poultry, and herbal remedies in companion animals for arthritis and stress. This paper aims to bridge ancient Ayurvedic principles with modern veterinary research, highlighting both opportunities and

challenges for integration. To use Ayurvedic therapies effectively, it is not necessary to have an understanding of the basic philosophy of Ayurveda. Modern veterinarians can use Ayurvedic herbal therapies on the basis of the scientifically determined pharmacologic actions of the botanical compounds contained in these formulas. A large volume of basic and clinical research has been undertaken on the herbs of Ayurveda. Thus, in the World scientific literature, documentation is available that enables the veterinary practitioner to evaluate herb safety, efficacy, and dosing. Veterinary herbal medicine includes plant-based treatments and therapeutic, for preventive or diagnostic purposes in the field of animal health care. The use of herbal medicine in both human and animal health care has a long history, dating back thousands of years.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda; Pasu-Ayurveda; Veterinary medicine; Sharir Siddhanta; Herbal formulations; Livestock health; One Health; Ethnoveterinary; Holistic animal care; Indian medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda means, literally, "the Science of Life." Ayurveda is an ancient healing system that has its roots in India. Ayurveda is more than simply a collection of procedures and therapies: Ayurveda is a way of life that relates an individual's existence to universal principles. As a holistic healing system, Ayurveda encompasses not just the treatment of disease, but also the creation and maintenance of individual health and optimal wellness. It is comprehensive and holistic system that emphasizes living in accordance with the laws of nature and the universe. Health in ayurveda arises from this harmonious integration of the individual structures with the nature and the universe.^[1]

The actual practice of Ayurvedic medicine involves the combined use of herbs, diet, massage, exercise, detoxification, and meditation. These therapies are prescribed to the patient as a result of the patient's Ayurvedic diagnosis.

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, surrounds a comprehensive framework of health that includes not only human wellbeing but also the care of animals (*Pasu-Ayurveda*).^[2] and plants (*Vriksha-Ayurveda*). Rooted in the Vedas, particularly the *Atharvaveda*, and systematized through classical treatises such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, Ayurvedic knowledge represents a deeply integrated system of ecological and physiological balance. Within this framework, animals are not simply functional property

but are seen as essential contributors to the global and agricultural system, deserving of health, dignity, and systematic care.

Veterinary medicine within Ayurveda, known as *Pasu-Ayurveda*. Numerous illustrations of veterinary medicine based on the holistic approach of *Ayurveda* have been mentioned in the *Garuda Purana*, *Agni Purana*, *Atri-Samhita*, *Matsya purana*, and many other ancient works of literature. Epics such as *Mahabharata* depicts the treatment of thousands of injured animals by experts such as prince *Nakula*, who specialized in treating horses, and prince *Sahadeva*, in treating cows. Ayurveda treatises namely *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, and *Harita Samhita* contain many allusions to animal care and treatment. However, *Shalihotra*, *Palkapya* and *Atreya* were among the most admirable and well-regarded veterinary science scholars who contributed unique works to developing *Ashwa-ayurveda*, *Gaj- ayurveda*, and *Gav ayurveda*. These ancient experts have written various treatises on veterinary medicine, surgery, and ethics and are still popular among scholars working in *Pasu ayurveda*. In *Sharir sthana* of *Charaka Samhita* describes the interconnection of all conscious beings through the concept of *Loka Samya Purush*—the reflection of the universe within the individual existence.^[3]

This principle supports the application of Ayurvedic *Tridosha Siddhanta (Vata, Pitta, Kapha)* which can be used not only in humans but also in animals, with species-specific variations. For example, in cattle, symptoms of excessive *Pitta* may present as pharyngeal inflammatory disorders such as mastitis, while *Kapha* disturbances may observed as slow digestion and mucous congestion. Ayurveda medicines and therapies have found growing application in veterinary practice. For instance:

Table No 1: Conditions & Ayurvedic medicines in Veterinary use.

Conditions	Ayurvedic Medicines (Vet use)
<i>Dermatitis</i>	1. Panchanimbadi churna 2. Gandhak rasayan 3. Panchtikta ghrita 4. Mahamanjistharist 5. Khadirarist
<i>Diarrhea</i>	1. Kutajparpati vati 2. Gangadhar churn 3. Bilvadi churn
Acidity/Vomiting/Nausea	1. Pittashekhar rasa 2. Avipattikar churn
Anorexia	1. Chitrakadi vati

	2. Arogyavardhani vati
Paralysis	1. Ekangaveer rasa 2. Maharasnaadi kwath 3. Rasraj ras 4. Yogendra ras 5. Pravaal pisti
Epilepsy	1. Sankhapuspi syrup 2. Saraswatarista 3. Bramhi vati 4. Smriti sagar ras 5. Balarista 6. Ashwagandha churn 7. Dashmoolarist

Procedures like *Vamana* (therapeutic vomiting), *Virechana* (therapeutic purgation), *Basti* (medicinal enema), *Nasya* (dosing medicines via the nose), and *Raktamokshana* (bloodletting through multiple ways) are all part of Ayurveda. A key phase in *Panchakarma* is *Basti*, which involves administering medicinal oils, or liquids down the rectum. The medications in the oil or decoction have a synergistic effect after being absorbed in the intestines. In modern medicine, enemas are usually given as the final option for lower gastrointestinal cleansing. However, the *Basti* process outlined in Ayurvedic literature has a broad therapeutic effect on practically every biological tissue, including advantages for reproduction, healing, prevention, and health promotion.^[4]

Basti Karma is divided into two categories based on the quality of the drugs: *Sneha Basti* (*Anuvasana*) and *Niruha Basti* (*Aasthapan*). The term "*Niruha*" denotes "to eliminate" or "to eliminate" diseases from the body, whereas "*Asthapan*" means "to establish life span and age".

- It nourishes the body and balances Vata and other doshas.
- Vata is generally located in colon.
- Therapeutic ayurveda *Abhyangam* and *Swedan* (massage and steam) bring doshas from all over the body to the abdomen, which are then removed through *Basti* therapy.^[5]

Basti Chikitsa (Medicated Enema) in Animal^[6]

Basti Karma is one of the modalities among the five biocleansing /detoxifying procedures (*Panchakarma* procedures/ *Samshodhan Chikitsa*). Some drugs are absorbed by passive diffusion and some by active transport, bioavailability of the medicine, will be higher when given as *Basti*.

Table No-2 Basti Chikitsa in Animal.

Animal	Basti (Enema nozzle)	Netra pot	Anuvasan Basti Matra (Dose)	Asthapan Basti Matra (Dose)	Basti Dravya (Medicine used)
Elephant	1 Aratni (approx. 40 cm)		2 Prastha (approx. 1280 ml)	4 Aadhak (approx. 10 l)	Aswatha, Vata, Aswakarna, Khadira, Aaragvadha, Shal, Tala
Camel	18 Angula (approx. 32 cm)		1 Prastha (approx. 640 ml)	2 Aadhak (approx. 5 l)	Pilu, Karir, Khadira, Aaragvadha, Dashmoola
Horse and Cow	16 Angula (approx. 28 cm)		4 to 6 Pala (approx. 160 to 240 ml)	3 Prastha (approx. 2 l)	For Horse: Palash, Danti, Devdaru, Katruna, Dravanti For Cow: Mudgaparni, Mashaparni, Dhava, Shigru, Patla, Madhook, Danti, Chitrak, Palash, Ajmoda, Devdaru, Kutaki
Goat and Sheep	10 Angula (approx. 18 cm)		2 Pala (approx. 80 ml)	1 Prastha (approx. 640 ml)	Triphala, Parushak, Badar, Kapittha

Thus, veterinary Ayurveda follows the basic Ayurvedic principles (Siddhanta) but adapts them to the physiological and behavioral characteristics of different species. As part of this rejuvenating therapy, elephants get Snana, Abhyanga, and Dhumapan as part of their care regimen. Horses are considered to be sattvic animals, horses are given treatments based on Ashva ayurveda that emphasize endurance, digestion, and joint health.^[7] Due to their sacred place in Indian tradition, cattle are often the primary recipients of Ayurvedic veterinary treatments, particularly for reproductive and lactation problems.

Ayurvedic Medicines Used in Veterinary Practice^[8,9]

Several Ayurvedic formulations mentioned in classical texts have been adapted for animal healthcare. It presents an overview of commonly used Ayurvedic herbs and polyherbal formulations with corresponding veterinary applications.

Table No-3 Ayurvedic Medicines used in Veterinary Practice.

Ayurvedic Name	Botanical Name	Classical Use	Modern Veterinary Application	Target Species
Ashwagandha	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Balya, Rasayana	Anti-stress, fertility booster	Cattle, Dogs
Haridra	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Kustha, Vrana, Raktashodhaka	Antibacterial, skin disorders	Dogs, Equines
Shatavari	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Stanyajanana, Rejuvenator	Enhances milk yield, uterine tonic	Cows, Buffaloes
Amalaki	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	Rasāyana,	Immune booster,	Poultry, Canines

		Vayasthāpana	antioxidant	
Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Krimighna, Twachya	Ectoparasitidal, anti-fungal	Poultry, Cattle
Triphala Churna	—	Rejuvenator, Digestive	Constipation, gut flora modulation	Ruminants
Dashamoola Kwatha	—	Vāta-nāśaka	Lameness, joint inflammation	

Ayurvedic medicines have been given to animals around the world, especially in rural areas, for cohorts. These remedies, used for common problems in animals such as wounds, infections, or gastric problems, often originate from plants readily available in the area. Farmers still use them because they are generally economic and easy to prepare. Natural alternatives such as Ayurveda are currently receiving more attention due to growing concerns about drug resistance and chemical residues in meat and milk. This article assesses the benefits of Ayurvedic treatments, their use in veterinary medicine, and how further study can establish their validity as a component of contemporary animal care.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

However, conducting a thorough review of various contemporary medical literature sources, inadequate proof exists to support the presence of these significant contributions, scope, and limitations of animal studies in Ayurveda literature. Example: using search engines like PubMed, Google Scholar, and others to seek up a topic like Animal Studies for Contributions to Ayurveda fails to deliver any results that are enough for attributing their contribution to the literature on Ayurveda. Analyzing some of Ayurveda's primary contributions to our understanding of animal research in several Ayurvedic fields is the aim of this message. Ayurveda literature including the Sushruta Samhita, Dalhana commentary, and Chakrapani commentary are used as research tools in animal studies. The literature on contemporary animal research was compiled using a variety of search engines, including Google Scholar, Med Live, and Pub Med, AYUSH Research Portal, Scopus. The data from both fields of study have been compared and reviewed for critical analysis.

DISCUSSION

This research paper highlights the tremendous potential of Ayurvedic medicine in veterinary research and practice. The core principles of Ayurvedic medicine can be applied to animal health, creating an evidence-based approach to veterinary care that is ecologically conscious and culturally relevant. In short, with an extensive history of animal care, the ancient Ayurvedic system of medicine provides an established approach that can be modified to meet the needs

of current veterinary care. The use of the Tridosha theory, Dravyaguna science, and the medical center on animals provides an integrated approach. Ayurvedic veterinary medicine is consistent with the principles of One Health and global efforts to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic medicine has a lot of potential in the field of veterinary medicine, but it hasn't been completely utilized yet, particularly in India and other places with a tradition of plant-based therapy, according to an examination of a few chosen works of literature. Numerous traditional Ayurvedic writings, such as the Shalihotra Samhita, include comprehensive animal health formulations and treatment tenets, many of which are still used in rural communities today.^[10] Scientific support for these age-old methods has grown in recent years. For instance, a number of in vitro and in vivo investigations have shown that medicinal plants have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and immune-stimulating qualities. such as Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*), ashwagandha (*Withania somnifera*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and neem (*Azadirachta indica*) when used to treat common animal illnesses include mastitis, dyspepsia, wounds, and parasite infections.

Several peer-reviewed studies cited in Scopus- and PubMed-indexed journals have shown improved clinical outcomes in livestock. When Ayurvedic medicines were used as primary treatment or along with allopathic treatment. Improvements included a reduction in somatic cell count in mastitis cases, faster wound healing, improved appetite and digestion, and improved immunity against seasonal infections. Moreover, Ayurvedic formulas have shown benefits such as minimal drug withdrawal periods, low toxicity, and absence of drug residues in animal products such as milk and meat.

The integration of Ayurveda into veterinary medicine is no longer just a matter of cultural revival; it is a vital path towards sustainable, ethical and effective animal health care. Inspired by time-honored classics such as the Shalihotra Samhita, validated by contemporary ethno-veterinary practices, and supported by emerging scientific evidence, Ayurvedic veterinary medicine offers a biocompatible alternative to synthetic drugs. Its principles - which are rooted in the universal laws of tridosha, dhatu, and source - are not limited to the human body but are also applicable to animal physiology.

Finally, the scope of Ayurvedic medicine in veterinary research is not only broad but also

fundamental. Combining ancient science with modern needs can pave the way for a green revolution in veterinary healthcare. Future research, policy support, and clinical collaboration will be key to unlocking its full potential

Table No-4 Ayurvedic Principles in Animal Dosha Diagnosis.

Animal	Dominant Doṣa	Common Disorders	Suggested Ayurvedic Herbs
Cow	Kapha	Mastitis, Indigestion	Neem, Ashwagandha, Panchatikta
Dog	Vata–Pitta	Skin issues, Anxiety	Triphala, Brahmi, Dashamoola
Horse	Pitta	Heat Stroke, Colic	Shatavari, Guduchi, Chandana
Poultry	Vata	Respiratory Infections	Tulsi, Trikatu, Pippali

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